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EDGE DETECTION TECHNIQUES FOR IMAGE SEGMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Interpretation of image contents is one of the objectives in computer vision specifically in image processing. In this era it has received much awareness of researchers. In image interpretation the partition of the image into object and background is a severe step. Segmentation separates an image into its component regions or objects. Image segmentation t needs to segment the object from the background to read the image properly and identify the content of the image carefully. In this context, edge detection is a fundamental tool for image segmentation. In this paper an attempt is made to study the performance of most commonly used edge detection techniques for image segmentation and also the comparison of these techniques is carried out with an experiment by using MATLAB software.

KEYWORDS

Computer Vision , Image Segmentation , Edge detection, MATLAB.

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COMMON PHASES OF COMPUTER FORENSICS INVESTIGATION MODELS

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ABSTRACT

The increasing criminal activities using digital information as the means or targets warrant for a structured manner in dealing with them. Since 1984 when a formalized process been introduced, a great number of new and improved computer forensic investigation processes have been developed. In this paper, we reviewed a few selected investigation processes that have been produced throughout the years and then identified the commonly shared processes. Hopefully, with the identification of the commonly shard process, it would make it easier for the new users to understand the processes and also to serve as the basic underlying concept for the development of a new set of processes. Based on the commonly shared processes, we proposed a generic computer forensics investigation model, known as GCFIM.

KEYWORDS

Computer Forensic Models, Computer Forensic Investigation

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MACHINE LEARNING METHODS FOR SPAM E-MAIL CLASSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

The increasing volume of unsolicited bulk e-mail (also known as spam) has generated a need for reliable anti-spam filters. Machine learning techniques now days used to automatically filter the spam e-mail in a very successful rate. In this paper we review some of the most popular machine learning methods (Bayesian classification, k-NN, ANNs, SVMs, Artificial immune system and Rough sets) and of their applicability to the problem of spam Email classification. Descriptions of the algorithms are presented, and the comparison of their performance on the SpamAssassin spam corpus is presented.

KEYWORDS

Spam, E-mail classification, Machine learning algorithms

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IMPORTANCE OF DATA COLLECTION AND VALIDATION FOR SYSTEMATIC SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Systematic software development process involves estimation of size, effort, schedule and cost of a software project and analysis of critical factors affecting these estimates. In literature there are many methods for software estimation and categorization of critical factors. More than 50% of the projects undertaken have challenged the initially proposed estimates. Even if we consider updating estimates at various phases of software development, the percentage of challenged projects reduces marginally. The reason for such a situation is that the decisions are made on historical and collected data. Therefore, software data collection to a reasonable accuracy and its validation is important both for decision making and validating software development process. In this paper an effort is made to highlight the importance of software data collection. Collected data is utilized to validate effort estimation model formulated by the authors. Comparison of effort values obtained from popular estimation models is also made. The data collected has also helped in identifying the critical factors affecting the estimates.

KEYWORDS

Software Size, Effort, Cost, Schedule, Risk, Estimation.

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THE ANALYSIS OF THE TIME TABLE STRUCTURE WITHIN A STUDENT INFORMATION SYSTEM (SIS)

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ABSTRACT

This paper will show the result of the analysis and synthesis processes that take place when making a time table for a University Information System (UIS), especially for SIS. This proposed paper does the comparison between two methods of designing a time table, shows the advantages and disadvantages of these methods and more precisely how to implement each of them using programming languages.

KEYWORDS

Student Information System (SIS), Time table, Prerequisite courses, Flowchart.

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EVALUATION OF INFORMATION RETRIEVAL SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

One of the challenges of modern information retrieval is to adequately evaluate Information Retrieval System (IRS) in order to estimate future performance in a specified application domain. Since there are many algorithms in literature the decision to select one for usage depends mostly on the evaluation of the systems' performance in the domain. This paper presents how visual and scalar evaluation methods complement one another to adequately evaluate information retrieval systems. The visual evaluation methods are capable of indicating whether one IRS performs better than another IRS fully or partially. An overall performance of IRS is revealed using scalar evaluation methods. The use of both types of evaluation methods will give a clear picture of the performance of the IRSs. The Receiver Operator Characteristic (ROC) curve and Precision-Recall (P-R) curve were used to illustrate the visual evaluation methods. Scalar methods notably precision, recall, Area Under Curve (AUC) and F measure were used.

KEYWORDS

ROC curve, Precision, Recall, Area Under Curve, Information Retrieval System

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THE DEVELOPMENT OF ELECTRONIC PAYMENT SYSTEM FOR UNIVERSITIES IN INDONESIA: ON RESOLVING KEY SUCCESS FACTORS

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ABSTRACT

It is known that IT projects are high-risk. To achieve project success, the strategies to avoid and reduce risks must be designed meticulously and implemented accordingly. This paper presents methods for avoiding and reducing risks throughout the development of an information system, specifically electronic payment system to handle tuition in the universities in Indonesia. The university policies, regulations and system models are design in such a way to resolve the project key success factors. By implementing the proposed methods, the system has been successfully developed and currently operated. The research is conducted in Parahyangan Catholic University, Bandung, Indonesia.

KEYWORDS

university electronic payment system, tuition payment system, resolving key success factor, ensuring IS project success.

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SECURITY THREATS ON CLOUD COMPUTING VULNERABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Clouds provide a powerful computing platform that enables individuals and organizations to perform variety levels of tasks such as: use of online storage space, adoption of business applications, development of customized computer software, and creation of a “realistic” network environment. In previous years, the number of people using cloud services has dramatically increased and lots of data has been stored in cloud computing environments. In the meantime, data breaches to cloud services are also increasing every year due to hackers who are always trying to exploit the security vulnerabilities of the architecture of cloud. In this paper, three cloud service models were compared; cloud security risks and threats were investigated based on the nature of the cloud service models. Real world cloud attacks were included to demonstrate the techniques that hackers used against cloud computing systems. In addition, countermeasures to cloud security breaches are presented.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, cloud security threats and countermeasures, cloud service models

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COST BREAKDOWN OF PUBLIC CLOUD COMPUTING AND PRIVATE CLOUD COMPUTING AND SECURITY ISSUES

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this paper is to distinguish between the issues of private and public cloud computing and what are the challenges faced during Building up your own private and public cloud. which computing out if above two should be implemented in an organization.[12]

KEYWORDS

Public vs. Private cloud computing, Issues in private and public Cloud computing

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INCREASING THE TRANSISTOR COUNT BY CONSTRUCTING A TWO-LAYER CRYSTAL SQUARE ON A SINGLE CHIP

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ABSTRACT

According to the Moore's law, the number of transistor should be doubled every 18 to 24 months. The main factors of increasing the number of transistor are: a density and a die size. Each of them has a serious physical limitation; the first one "density" may be reached "Zero" after few years, which causes limitation in performance and speed of a microprocessor, the second one "die size" cannot be increased every 2 years, it must be fixed for several years, otherwise it will affect the economical side. This article aims to increase the number of transistors, which increase the performance and the speed of the microprocessor without or with a little bit increasing the die size, by constructing a two-layer crystal square for transistors, which allows increasing the number of transistors two additional times. By applying the new approach the number of transistors in a single chip will be approximately doubled every 24 months according to Moore's Law without changing rapidly the size of a chip (length and width), only the height of a chip must be changed for putting the two layers.

KEYWORDS

Moore's Law, Crystal square, Density, Die size, Number of transistors, Feature size, Design complexity.

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